

THE IMPORTANCE OF PLAYING INTELLECTUAL GAMES

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Abstract: in this article you will be given information about the number of benefits of playing brain games and answer the main question (why are the brain games essential for people, especially for kids). Additionally, you will be given some intellectual game in order to practice playing ones.

Key words: improving, short memory-term, enhanced mood, improve creativity and mental flexibility, good concentration.

Games and fun activities are an integral part of teaching English as a foreign language. As Rustamova (2022) stated whether you're teaching adults or children, games will enliven your lesson and ensure your children leave the classroom wanting more. Games can be used to warm up the class before your lesson begins, during class to give children a break when you're tackling a difficult topic, or at the end of class when you have a few minutes to kill. There are literally hundreds, if not thousands, of games you can play with your children. EFL games are used to test vocabulary, practice conversation, learn tenses - the list is endless. This list of ten classic ESL games every teacher should know will help you get started and feel prepared. Having these on hand before you enter class will ensure that your lessons run smoothly, and if things get a little out of hand, you can grab the attention of the class in no time. Playing brain games is one of the crucial process people do in their daily life. In addition, parents pay attention for increasing brains and memories of their children. Because, young generation gain the main knowledge, making up 75% information until 5 years old. Therefore, parents teach to play simple brain games for their children. If parents pay attention for this, it helps to increase concentration and interests to get knowledge. Most importantly, playing brain games are very important to upbringing creative youth. Engaging in cognitively stimulating activities and brain training over the course of life can positively impact how well your brain functions, including memory attention, thinking, language and increasing skills. You are given extra information for elderly people, despite lack of scientific evidence and experiment, playing online or offline brain games can help maintain or improve brain health.

The aim of this article is explained the benefits of playing brain games for people. Finally, you will be given one intellectual game to explain how to play mind games. There can be the number of cons of playing brain games such as: firstly, releasing stress and this helps to prevent mental problem caused by stress and nerve, as a result, it provides with enhanced mood. Secondly, you increase memory by playing intellectual games, since brain games raise action of mind in order to develop memory. One of the best benefit is improved focus and concentration and kids will become better at certain thinking and learning skills. The next benefit is improved creativity and mental flexibility, as well as enhanced thinking and reaction time. Finally, playing brain games helps to build self-esteem step by step by losing your fear.

I recommend you online and offline games. This game which is called “Memory” ranks high in the recommended brain games for kids as it helps improve the memory. The objective of the game is to uncover all the similarly paired flashcards on a grid. A maximum of two cards can be revealed simultaneously after which the picture inscribed on them is hidden. Only if the cards are similar will their picture side be shown permanently. In this way, your child must remember the correct location of the cards to uncover all of them.

Crosswords are one of the most classic brain training games for all ages. These games can help test your vocabulary skills and draw on knowledge from history, science and popular culture. You can perform crosswords online or through gaming apps or go with the more traditional route, such as printed books or newspapers. Crosswords are often used as a cognitive exercise to delay the onset of dementia, especially when made into a regular habit. Focus on puzzles that are challenging and keep your brain engaged. Because it is possible to strain you brain, limit yourself to one challenging puzzle per day. Furthermore, there are the number of simple games such as chess, concentration and so on to improve memory. If this games are played per day, it is the best way of brain improvement for all ages people.

To conclude, these games will keep your children engaged and happy as they learn! Remember, there are hundreds of different EFL games you can play with your children. As you build confidence in class, you can start putting your own spin on games and eventually come up with your own spin. Regardless of the age of your children, they are guaranteed to enjoy playing EFL games in the classroom. An EFL classroom should be fun, active and challenging and these games are sure to get you started.

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